

MICROSCOPIC ANATOMY OF THE PANCREAS OF EMU BIRD

N. Rajendran, A.K. Gautam, A. Prasanth Babu and
T.S. Chandrasekhara Rao

Department of Veterinary Anatomy and Histology, College of Vety. Science,
Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India

(Received : 31-03-2009; Accepted : 26-06-2009)

The paucity of literature on histology of pancreas of emu enthused to undertake the present study.

Materials and Methods

Six adult emu birds irrespective of sex were utilized for the present study. The birds were used for commercial purpose. Tissue pieces from the dorsal; ventral and splenic lobes of the pancreas and its ducts were collected after slaughtering the birds. The tissues were processed for paraffin sections which were subjected to routine Haematoxylin and Eosin and also special histological staining method like Van Giesons; Weigerts and Wilders method for collagen, elastic and reticular fibers respectively (Singh and Sulochana 1997).

Results and Discussion

The pancreas of emu birds was made up of exocrine and endocrine portions. The bulk of gland was formed by exocrine tissue consisted of serous compound tubulo alveolar acini arranged concentrically around the islets of langerhans (Fig.1). The gland was enclosed by a thin fibrous capsule. The capsule was made up of collagen and reticular fibers and a few elastic fibers. Similar observations were seen in fowl (Hodges 1974) in turkey (Malewitz and Calhoun (1957) in Japanese quail (Shivakumar 1997) and in domestic duck (Madhavi *et al.* 2000).

The pancreas in emu was compact with indistinct connective tissue septa. The interacinar connective tissue composed only reticular fibers around the acini (Fig.2). The collagens tissue was confined to the capsule, ducts, blood vessels and their vicinity. Lymphocytic granulocytes and undifferentiated cells were observed beneath the capsule. Similar findings were reported by Hodges (*loc. cit*) in fowl.

The acinar cells were pyramidal in shape and the lumen was narrow and the cell boundaries were indistinct as in turkey (Malewitz and Calhoun *loc. cit*). Often cleft like inertcellular spaces were observed between acinar cells within the acini as reported earlier in duck (Das and Biswal, 1967) and Japanese quail (Shivakumar, *loc. cit*). Contrary to the findings of Shivakumar (*loc. cit*) in Japanese quail a distinct basement membrane around acini was not observed as in the case of duck (Madhavi *et al. loc. cit*). Absence of basket cells around acini was in accordance with the findings of Madhavi *et al. (loc. cit)* in duck. The nucleus of the acinar cells was located in the basal half of the cells. Similar observations were reported by Calhoun (1954) and Hodges (*loc. cit*) in fowl; Malewitz and Calhoun (*loc. cit*) in turkey, Shivakumar (*loc. cit*) in Japanese quail and Madhavi *et al, (loc. cit)* in duck. The cytoplasm in the basal one third of acinar cells was dense; finely granular and basophilic; while in apical two third normally filled with coarse eosinophilic

Fig. 1: Photomicrograph of pancreas of emu bird showing exocrine (EX), Endocrine (EN) Alpha Cells (A) and Beta Cells (B). H&E x 400

granules. These findings coincide with the reports of Hodges (*loc.cit*) in fowl; Das and Biswal (*loc.cit*) and Madhavi *et al.* (*loc.cit*) in duck and Shivakumar (*loc.cit*) in Japanese quail.

Three types of acinar cells resting, active and exhausted were identified in a section of pancreas based on the nuclear and cytoplasmic appearance. However, all the cells in a single acinus were in similar state of activity. In resting cells the nucleus was oval and heterochromatic. The zymogen granules in the cytoplasm were abundant and filled a large proportion of the cells. In active cells nucleus was spherical to oval and the chromatin was intermediate in appearance. The zymogen granules were moderate in amount. In exhausted cells, the nucleus was spherical, large, euchromatic and was more distinct. The zymogen granules were least in amount and basal cytoplasm was more intensely basophilic. These observations were similar with the findings of Madhavi *et al.* (*loc.cit*) in duck. The centroacinar cells were observed occasionally in acinar lumen. Das and Biswal (*loc.cit*) and Madhavi *et al.* (*loc.cit*) in duck and Shivakumar (*loc.cit*) in Japanese quail observed the centroacinar

Fig. 2: Photomicrograph of pancreas of emu bird showing Reticular fibers (RF) Gridley's x 400

cells in some of the acini. Presence of centroacinar cells were also reported in fowl (Calhoun, *loc.cit*), duck (Braun Blanquet, 1969) and turkey (Malewitz and Calhoun, *loc.cit*). The centroacinar cells were elongated and showed clear cytoplasm as reported by Braun Blanquet (*loc.cit*) in duck.

The pancreatic acini emptied into intermediate tubules through intercalated ducts. The intercalated ducts and intermediate tubules were lined by simple squamous epithelium. The slender intermediate tubules which were quite larger than intercalated ducts were seldom seen in sections as reported by Hodges (*loc.cit*) in fowl. In the present study due to absence of lobulation various orders of duct system like intralobular and interlobular ducts were not distinguished as reported by Calhoun (*loc.cit*) in fowl and Madhavi (*loc.cit*) in duck.

The intraglandular ducts were larger and lined by simple cuboidal epithelium and showed secretory material in their lumen. The extra glandular ducts possessed 3 layer i.e. tunica mucosa; tunica muscularis and tunica adventia. The tunica mucosa was lined by simple columnar epithelium. The

tunica muscularis was thick and consisted of an outer circular and an inner longitudinal layer of smooth muscle fibers. These observations were in agreement with the findings of Hodges (*loc.cit*) in fowl, and Madhavi *et al.* (*loc.cit*) in duck. Contrary to this Shivakumar (*loc.cit*) described tunica muscularis was having an inner circular and an outer longitudinal layer in Japanese quail. He also stated that the goblet cells were observed in epithelium which, however were not encountered in this study.

The endocrine portion of the pancreas of emu bird was composed of roughly spherical islets of langerhans surrounded by a layer of collagens and reticular fibers. The presence of reticular capsule around the islets was in accordance with the findings of Madhavi *et al.* (*loc.cit*) in duck and Calhoun (*loc.cit*) in fowl.

The islets of langerhans were mainly of two types i.e. alpha and beta similar to the findings of Calhoun (*loc.cit*) in turkey, Madhavi *et al.* (*loc.cit*) in duck and in Japanese quail (Shivakumar, *loc.cit*). Alpha cells were columnar in shape with oval and round nucleus containing one or two nuclei. Beta cells were polygonal in shape with rounded to ovoid nuclei and cytoplasm constituted fine granules which stained blue gray to purple with routine staining. These findings were in accordance with the findings of Hodges (*loc.cit*) in fowl.

Summary

In the present study on histology of pancreas of emu birds, based on nuclear and cytoplasmic appearance three types of acinar cells i.e. resting, active and

exhausted were identified. The zymogen granules were abundant in resting cells, moderate in active cells and least in exhausted state. The acini emptied into intermediate tubules through intercalated ducts both of which were lined by simple squamous epithelium. The large ducts were lined by simple cuboidal epithelium while the extragranular ducts showed tunica mucosa, tunica muscularis and tunica adventia. The islets of langerhans constituted mainly columnar alpha and polygonal beta cells. Alpha cells were columnar in shape while the beta cells were polygonal in shape.

References

- Braun Blanquet, M.(1969)... *Acta Anatomica* **20** : 164-94.
- Calhoun, M.L. (1954)... *The Microscopic Anatomy of the Digestive system of the Chicken*. pp. 82 Iowa state college press, Ames, Iowa.
- Das, L.N and Biswal G.(1967)... *Indian Vet. J.* **44** : 763-66.
- Hodges, R.D. (1974)... *The Histology of the Domestic fowl*. pp.101-08 Academic press; London.
- Madhavi, G Rao, T.S.C; Pramod Kumar, D; Nagamalleswari, Y. and Sreenu, M (2000)... *Indian Journal of Animal Science* **70(2)** : 126-128.
- Malewitz, D and Calhoun, M.L (1957)... *Poultry Science.*, **37** : 388-98.
- Shivakumar M. (1997)... PhD. Thesis submitted to Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University; Madras.
- Singh, U.B and Sulochana,S. (1997)... *A practical manual of Histological and Histochemical Techniques*. p-12-101. Kothari publications, Mumbai.